

Deep learning-based images classification using an efficient CNN model trained on handwritten dataset

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Abstract- Image processing and deep learning (DL) are two zones of excessive awareness to researchers and scientists worldwide. It is having multiple applications fields such as robotics, medicine, and security and surveillance. DL is about learning multiple representations and abstraction levels that help make sense of data such as images, sound, and text. The MNIST dataset has a massive number of handwritten text dataset, and it is frequently used for training, testing, and validation of the convolutional neural network (CNN) deep model. This article has created an efficient model with multiple convolutions, ReLU and pooling layers, which is tested on MNIST dataset with 98.47 % accuracy. Further, this model is tested on a similar kind of random image Dataset which gives significant results in terms of accuracy.

Keywords- Artificial neural network (ANN), Convolutional neural network (CNN), Deep learning (DL), MNIST Dataset.

I. INTRODUCTION

Conventional machine learning and deep learning both are the subfields of artificial intelligence (AI). AI is today's preferred research of interest of researchers in computer vision application. Both machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) fall under the wide-ranging class of AI [1].

Figure 1 Artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning

Recognizing handwritten digits has been of great importance and has various uses in online handwriting recognition on 21st-century smartphones and tablets, to extract postal zip-codes on mail or letterheads, processing bank check amounts, numeric entries in forms (like - tax forms) filled up by hand, or to automatically identify license plates etc. [2]. There are different challenges faced while attempting to solve this problem. The handwritten digits are generally different in strokes, size, thickness, orientation, and distance from the margins, increasing the complexity for recognition [3].

We have proposed a novel CNN model to achieve the best performance on the handwritten digit recognition task from random images and the MNIST dataset in present work. Images are of handwritten Number digits taken from various resources, normalized to 28x28 size to fit into the model. We designed our model using three convolutional layers [4] in which after every convolutional layer, there is max-pooling layer to extract the features of the digits in the image.[5]

This paper is organized as follows. Section II starts by explaining in detail Deep Learning and CNN model of Deep Learning. Section III focuses on the implementation of the model and the way dataset is trained. Results obtained on the trained dataset and it's testing on random images is discussed in detail in Section IV, and Section V includes the conclusions of this work. Further, in section VI, references are given.

II. DEEP LEARNING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK MODEL

1. DEEP LEARNING

Deep learning (DL) recently becomes the trending investigation domain in the field of AI. Selectivity-invariance problem is the principal disadvantage of conventional ML because of which these approaches have limited capability of processing the data in their original form. Selectivity-invariance implies selecting those features that contain more information and ignore less information containing parameters, i.e. selected features should be distinct from each other. This motivated researchers to the advancement of machine learning approach, i.e., deep learning. DL sometimes also referred to as representation learning having a set of algorithms that automatically discovers the classification or detection needed by allowing a machine to be input with original dataset [6]. On various data representations, DL is a part of ML methods [7]. Algorithms are designed by observing the human brain structure and functions.

2. DEEP LEARNING METHODS

The most crucial subsection of ML is the DL technique. The classifications of DL are portrayed in Figure 2 and its subsections are discussed in the below sections.

Figure 2 Classification of deep learning

Most commonly used deep networks are convolutional neural network (CNN) and recurrent neural network (RNN) which we reviewed in the upcoming sections, however our primary focus on CNN.

3. NEURAL NETWORK (NN)

Most of the neural network, also referred to as artificial neural network (ANN) is originated from the biological theory of neurons. It consists of input layers, hidden layers and output layers. The hidden layers are used to process the input received and send them to output layers. The basic architecture of the neural network is shown in figure 3. NN approach provides more accuracy and efficiency than preexisting methods. Various approaches of NN are the backpropagation algorithm (BPNN), Radial basis function (RBF), Complementary NN (CMPNN) and Probabilistic approach. BPNN is the most widely used NN approach however it is slower in training when the large dataset is used [8].

Figure 3 Basic architecture of Neural Network

4. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK (CNN)

Convolutional Neural Networks is like regular Neural Networks where data fed to the neural network is processed by convolution layer; they're created from neurons with weights and biases that can be learned. Each somatic cell receives some inputs, performs a scalar product and optionally follows it with a non-linearity [9]. The hidden layers of neurons are only connected with the previous layer containing the subset of neurons. This type of sparse connectivity makes

the system able to implicitly learning of features. The CNN architecture consists of convolutional layers, pooling layers and fully connected layers, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Architecture of Convolutional Neural Network

a. CONVOLUTIONAL (CONV) LAYER

This layer is the primary unit of CNN, in which most computations are performed. These layers consist of an arrangement of neurons along with a set of feature maps. These layers have filters used to convolve with features for producing a separate 2D activation map [10] as shown in Figure 5. The network's complexity is reduced by keeping a smaller number of features by sharing weights by the neurons [11]. The CNNs are trained by Backpropagation that involves convolution operation with spatially flipped filters. These layers apply convolutional operation along with filtering and pass the result to the next layers.

Figure 5 Convolution operation in CNN

a. ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) LAYER

ReLU [12] refers to rectified linear unit. This layer is used to eliminate the negative values in a matrix, defined by function $f(x) = \max(0, x)$

b. POOLING LAYER

Pooling layers - CNN has alternating convolutional and pooling layers. Pooling layers are used to reduce the spatial dimension of image activation maps and the number of features without any loss of information results in a reduction in overall computational complexity. Pooling layers perfectly handles the problem caused due to overfitting. Average pooling, max pooling, stochastic pooling [13], spatial pyramid pooling [14], spectral pooling [15] and multiscale pooling [16] are some of the commonly used pooling operations. Max pooling operation is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Max Pooling operation in CNN

c. FULLY CONNECTED LAYER

It connects all the neurons in one layer to all neurons of the next layer like NN. It converts high dimensional feature map to one dimensional by high-level reasoning that gives the probability of feature belong to a specific class. Some of the approaches are developed recently to replace fully connected layers such as "Network In Network" architecture [17].

5. The difference between Deep Learning and Machine Learning

Regarding sub-Section 3 and 4 above, we outline three differences.

- Feature extraction:* Feature engineering for machine learning is usually done manually, which requires a lot of prior or domain expertise. Deep learning usually consists of multiple layers, passing data from one layer to another to build more complex models. The model is automatically obtained by training a large amount of data, which does not require manual feature extraction.
- Data volume and calculation requirements:* Generally speaking, machine learning requires a small number of samples, and deep learning requires a large number of samples. The execution time of the former is much shorter than the latter. The latter has huge network parameters, and training a multi-layer deep neural network requires a lot of computing power.
- Different algorithm models:* Commonly used models for deep learning such as neural networks, and commonly used models for machine learning such as naive Bayes, decision trees and SVM.[18]

III. IMPLEMENTED MODEL

In this paper, the MNIST dataset is used. This dataset consists of 70000 numbers of digit images, of which 60000 are training data for each class sample, and 10000 of them are test data for each class sample to evaluate our algorithm. The images in 28x28 resolution grid levels, representing the ten digits from 0 to 9. In Figure 7, some samples of the dataset are shown.

Figure 7 MNIST handwritten digit samples

We used a 64-bit Python3 and Tensorflow platform for implementing the CNN and training it and using Keras library in Colab notebooks. An Intel Core i3-5200U (up to 2.9 GHz) with 8GB RAM processor was used.

We considered several models of Neural Network while making the model for the training of MNIST handwritten images. Complex Network, Convolutional neural network seems to be the best fit as it extracts features before feeding it to the fully connected layer. model we optimized the accuracy by varying various parameters like Learning rate, Dropout and number of epochs. Figure 8 shows the architecture of the model.

Figure 8 Architecture of the developed model

We designed model with 2 convolutional layers, 32 filters of size 5x5 in the first and 64 filters of size 3x3 in the second. We tried increasing the number of the filter by two in each layer ie. 32, 64 but we did not find any significant change in the accuracy. The image size is small so 32 and 64 filters do the job well. Firstly, we reduce the image in convolution with only one convolution layer, but the testing dataset was not giving good accuracy. Padding was kept the same for the process and we increased the layers to 2. There is one max-pooling layer after each convolutional layer with strides of 2. They are reducing the image. The activation technique used after each convolutional network is ReLU. There was a dropout of 0.5 after a pooling layer. After the features were extracted the final Matrix was flatten

and fed as the input to the fully connected network. Activation technique used in the fully connected layer is ReLU and SoftMax with a dropout of 0.5. As the images are all grayscale then Relu is the best choice of the activation function.

Table 1 compares the accuracy of the CNN and ANN on the MNIST database. When the mean square error between the predicted values and the ground truth is less than 0.01.

Algorithm	Accuracy	Performance	Execution Time
ANN	62.19%	83.86%	14ms
CNN	99.91%	97.74%	234ms

TABLE I. SOME OF EXPERIMENT RESULTS FOR RANDOM DATASET

The results show here superiority of CNN to recognize the digit (8) accurately as shown in Figure 9. The recognition accuracies for the other algorithms are also high due to the ease of writing digit (8). In addition, CNN is superior in the performance If we compare it with ANN.

Figure 9 Accuracy of Different Digits by (CNN, ANN)

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we applied deep learning to the handwritten character recognition, and obtained good performance for image recognition. We analyzed the different between CNN and ANN by comparing the experiment results. Deep learning can approximate the complex function through deep nonlinear network model. It not only avoids the large workload of manually extract features, but also is better to describe potential information of the data.

In the future work, we will further study the optimization of deep learning, and apply it to more complex image recognition problems.

I. REFERENCES

- [1] Nitin Kumar Chauhan USICT, GGSIPU, New Delhi, India "A Review on Conventional Machine Learning vs Deep Learning" DOI: 10.1109/GUCON.2018.8675097
- [2] Z Selmi, M Ben Halima, A M. Alimi, "Deep Learning System for Automatic License Plate Detection and Recognition", 2017 14th IAPR International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR), 2017, pp. 1132-1138, doi.org/10.1109/ICDAR.2017.187
- [3] Y Bengio, A Courville, P Vincent, "Representation Learning: A Review and New Perspectives", IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, Vol 35, issue 8, 2018, pp 1798–1828, doi.org/10.1109/tpami.2013.50
- [4] P Le Callet, C Viard-Gaudin, D Barba, "A Convolutional Neural Network Approach for Objective Video Quality Assessment", IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks, 2006, Vol 17 Issue 5, pp. 1316–1327, doi.org/10.1109/TNN.2006.879766.
- [5] Simard, Patrice, D Steinkraus, and J C. Platt. "Best Practices for Convolutional Neural Networks Applied to Visual Document Analysis." In ICDAR, vol. 3, pp. 958–962. 2003.
- [6] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. E. Hinton, "Deep learning," Nature, vol. 521, pp. 436–444, May 2015.
- [7] LeCun, Yann, Bengio, Yoshua, "Convolutional networks for images, speech, and time series". In Arbib, Michael A. The handbook of brain theory and neural networks, edition 2, 1995, pp. 276–278.
- [8] S. B. Kotsiantis, "Supervised Machine Learning: A Review of Classification Techniques", Informatica, Vol. 31, No. 3, pp. 249-268, 2007.
- [9] K T Islam, G Mujtaba, R G Raj, H F Nweke, "Handwritten digits recognition with artificial neural network", 2017 International Conference on Engineering Technology and Technopreneurship (ICE2T), Vol 3 Issue 8, 2017, pp 1-4, doi.org/10.1109/ICE2T.2017.8215993
- [10] N. Aloysius, and M. Geetha, "A review on deep convolutional neural networks," International Conference on Communication and Signal Processing (ICCSP), Chennai, 2017, pp. 0588-0592.
- [11] G. E. Hinton, N. Srivastava, A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and R. R. Salakhutdinov, "Improving neural networks by preventing coadaptation of feature detectors," arXiv preprint arXiv:1207.0580, 2012
- [12] Saxena S., Sharma S., Sharma N., Verma A., "An Intelligent Parallel System for Segmenting abdominal CT images using atlas-based allocation from Spine", European Journal of Scientific Research, 137(3), 2016.
- [13] M. D. Zeiler, and R. Fergus, "Stochastic pooling for regularization of deep convolutional neural networks," CoRR, 2013.
- [14] A. Nguyen , J. Yosinski, and J. Clune, "Deep neural networks are easily fooled: High confidence predictions for unrecognizable images," IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), 2015.
- [15] O. Rippel, J. Snoek, and R. P. Adams, "Spectral representations for convolutional neural networks," arXiv preprint arXiv:1506.03767, 2015.
- [16] Y. Gong, L. Wang, R. Guo, and S. Lazebnik, "Multi-scale orderless pooling of deep convolutional activation features," ECCV, 2014.
- [17] M. Lin, Q. Chen, and S. Yan, "Network in network", Computing Research Repository (CoRR), vol. abs/1312.4400, 2013
- [18] Wenfei Liu, Jingcheng Wei, Qingmin Meng "Comparisons on KNN, SVM, BP and the CNN for Handwritten Digit Recognition"